

Complex Formation of Vanadium(V) with N-AHA : Extractive Photometric Methods of Determination of Trace Vanadium in Geological Materials and Alloy and Extraction Constants

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Reactions of vanadium(V) with N-anthranilohydroxamic acid under varying conditions of pH and acidity and extraction behaviour of the complexes in methyl isobutyl ketone is reported. New sensitive and selective photometric methods for trace determination of vanadium(V) in absence or presence of thiocyanate and its applications in the analyses of high speed steel, ilmenite and bauxite are described. The stepwise stability and extraction constants have been determined by absorptometric methods and reported.

CHELATING reagent N-anthranilohydroxamic acid (N-AHA) reported previously^{1,2} for spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) and manganese(II) and other acids³⁻⁵ are hitherto less utilized for studying complex formation reactions and solvent extraction of vanadium(V). Vanadium chelates of hydroxamic acids are mostly non-extractable in organic solvents. Presence of alcohol is known to inhibit the reaction sensitivity of V(V) with N-aryhydroxylamine reagents and its effect in the present systems has been investigated. The use of an altogether different solvent methyl isobutyl ketone (mibk) as the extractant is found necessary for such investigations^{6,7}. Ti(IV) complexes of variable compositions have been reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁰. The role of synergism in presence of thiocyanate ion for V(V)-N-AHA system has also been reported¹¹. In this paper reactions of N-AHA with V(V) under varying conditions of pH as well as acidity of medium are described. Three different complex chelates extracted in mibk have the same composition bearing the same metal to reagent ratio (1 : 2). The stability and extraction constants have been determined by log-log plot in absorptometric methods. The extractive photometric methods have been highly selective since most metal ions do not interfere. Vanadium has been determined in high-speed alloy steel and geological materials like ilmenite (< 0.2% V) and bauxite, utilizing binary and ternary chelate extractions.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: A stock solution of vanadium was prepared, using ammonium vanadate (E. Merck), and standardized^{5,12}. Metal solutions of different strengths were made after proper dilution with double distilled water. The reagent,

anthranilohydroxamic acid (m.p. 149), was prepared following the method described earlier². Standard reagent solutions (0.1 to 1.0 % w/v) of desired strengths in pure mibk were used directly for extraction. A 2% aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate was standardized and used in ternary extraction. Other chemicals and reagents used in all spectrophotometric measurements were of A. R. or G. R. grade quality.

Apparatus: Absorbance measurements were made with a Hilger Uvispek and a Spectromon 204 spectrophotometers with matched 1 cm quartz or glass cells. A Systronics pH-meter, 324, was used for pH measurements.

General procedure :

(A) **Binary extraction (pH 3.2):** An aliquot of vanadium solution ($1.963 \times 10^{-3} M$) was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel and the pH/acidity was adjusted to the desired value. A desired amount of the reagent solution (3 ml of 1% in mibk) and 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl were added to 10 ml of the aqueous phase. Equal volume (10 ml) was maintained for each phase and the whole shaken well for 5 min. The orange-red complex extracted at pH 3.2 is drained out into a 50 ml beaker and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extraction is repeated with three 5 ml portions of the solvent. The extracts are combined and transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume is made up with pure solvent and allowed to stand for 1.5 hr. The absorbance of the complex is measured at 470 nm against solvent blank.

(B) **Binary extraction (acidity 1.8 M HCl):** For extraction procedure at 1.8 M HCl acidity, 5 ml of 0.2% reagent solution and 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl are added to an aliquot of vanadium solution and the

mixture is shaken for 2 min with 10 ml mibk when the orange-red complex initially formed at pH 3.2 is extracted. The acidity of the 10 ml aqueous phase is adjusted to 1.8 M HCl with 6 M HCl. The deep-blue complex is extracted for 4 min and the complex solution (25 ml) is prepared as usual. The absorbance is measured at 595 nm against solvent blank. A calibration curve is also constructed for unknown samples.

(C) *Ternary extraction (pH 0.95/0.16 M HCl)* : For ternary extraction, the orange-red complex is first extracted at pH 3.2 in 15 ml mibk using 5 ml of 1% reagent and 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl. To it is added 5 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate. The pH of the 15 ml aqueous phase is adjusted to 0.95 and the green complex is extracted for 12 min. The absorbance of the complex is measured following the process described above.

Procedure for steel analysis : 0.5 g of the steel sample is dissolved in 20 ml dilute sulphuric acid (1 : 1) and digested completely in the usual manner till strong fumes of sulphur trioxide are evolved. The digest is diluted with 50 ml water, boiled and filtered through Whatman no. 42. The residue is washed several times with hot acidulated (H_2SO_4) water and finally with hot water. The filtrate and washings are collected in a 250 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up.

An aliquot of steel solution is oxidised at room temperature with 0.1% $KMnO_4$ solution till the pink colour persists. This solution is added to a hot 15% NaOH solution in excess and the mixture is boiled. The precipitated metal hydroxide is filtered. The filtrates obtained by double precipitation technique are combined and boiled down to a low volume. The solution is cooled and the vanadium content is determined following the recommended procedures A, B and C. The absorbances of the extracts are measured at 470, 595 and 630 nm for the respective complexes and the metal content determined separately.

Procedure for mineral analysis :

Ilmenite : 0.5 g of finely powdered ore (200 mesh) is fused with 9 g potassium bisulphate and a few drops of sulphuric acid in a silica crucible over a low flame to avoid spurring and the mass is brought to a clear melt. After fusion, the mass is cooled and leached with 1 : 9 sulphuric acid. The solution is boiled and oxidised with a few drops of nitric acid and the iron and titanium precipitated as hydroxides with an excess of 15% NaOH solution. Any adsorbed vanadium is freed from the hydroxide by double precipitation method. All the filtrates are combined and the volume reduced to about 50 ml by boiling. The solution is transferred to a 100 ml standard flask and the volume made up with water.

An appropriate aliquot of the above solutions is taken and the vanadium content in each case is determined following the recommended procedures A, B and C. Fluoride is used as masking agent for any trace amount of iron and titanium in the solution.

Bauxite : 0.5 g of the bauxite sample is fused for 2 hr with sodium carbonate (3-4 g) and sodium hydroxides (1 g) in a nickel crucible. The melt is cooled and leached with hot water overnight. The aqueous extract contains vanadium and other insoluble materials along with iron and titanium. The solution is filtered, transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume is made up. An appropriate amount of the solution is taken and the vanadium content determined by the procedures.

Results and Discussion

Spectral characteristics : The absorbance spectrum of the binary and ternary vanadium(V) chelates revealed maxima at 470, 535 and 630 nm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorbance curve. 1 : V(V)N-AHA (pH 3.2), 2 : V(V) N-AHA (1.8 M HCl), 3 : V(V) N-AHA -SON (pH 0.95/ 0.16 M HCl)

The extractions are performed by adding 0.1 to 6 M HCl in a 10-15 ml volume of aqueous phase. The orange-red complex was always formed and extracted first from a solution at pH 3.2 adjusted by adding 0.5 ml of 0.1 M HCl. At $pH > 2.1$, orange-red colour changes to deep-blue with shift in maxima (470 nm). Also, a strong emulsion is formed while the deep-blue complex is extracted above 3 M HCl. Addition of acid together with reagent and thiocyanate, and also the formation of emulsion at pH higher than 2.5 adversely affect the procedure of green mixed-ligand complex. 2.5 ml of 0.1%, 4 ml of 0.2% and 2.5 ml of 1% reagent solution in mibk were found sufficient for full colour development of the respective complexes and their extractions. 3.5 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate is found sufficient and the optimum range is 3-10 ml. Although emulsion is formed with 2 ml reagent and above, it breaks up quickly. No emulsion is noticed with lower thiocyanate concentration, but the peak shifts towards 595 nm.

The binary extractions are completed within 4-5 min, but the ternary extraction requires 12-13 min.

Absorbance may be measured immediately except the orange-red complex at pH 3.2 which require 1.5 hr for equilibrium to be attained after extraction. All these coloured chelates in mibk solvent are highly stable for more than 48 hr at room temperature.

Calibration curve, optimum range and sensitivity : For solutions of varied vanadium(V) content fixed amounts of reagent (N-AHA) solutions and thiocyanate (ternary) were utilized in the above procedures and absorbance measured at 470 nm, 595 nm and 630 nm, respectively. The systems obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.2-7.5 (orange-red), 0.2-6.5 (blue) and 0.5-12 (green) ppm with optimum range (Ringbom's plot¹³) 2.5-6.5 ppm, 3-7 ppm and 2-7.5 ppm, respectively (Fig. 2). The % relative error per 1% absolute photometric error using Ayre's equation¹⁴ is 2.72 for each complex. The molar absorptivity values are 3.45×10^3 (470 nm), 3.06×10^3 (595 nm) and 6.75×10^3 (630 nm) litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The Sandell's¹⁵ sensitivities are 0.0148, 0.0167 and 0.0076 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ V(V).

Fig. 2. Calibration curves. I V(V) N-AHA (pH 3.2), II. V(V) N-AHA (1.8 M HCl), III V(V) N-AHA-SCN (pH 0.95/0.16 M HOI)

Interference studies : Solutions were prepared by the above procedures with 4 ppm of vanadium and different amounts of diverse ions at pH-acidity conditions. The ions were added with vanadium(V) solution before the addition of N-AHA or mibk. In general, Fe(III), Ti(IV), Mo(VI), Nb(V), W(VI), Zr(IV) and Hf(IV) interfered in the determinations but were tolerated at lower pH (≈ 2.5) with fluoride ion masking and separation by double precipitation as hydroxides when present in large excess amounts and subsequent fluoride ion masking for moderate excess. The methods involving double precipitation technique and subsequent masking by fluoride ion permits selective photometric determination in geological materials and alloy steel. The extractive photometric methods find accurate and precise application in the analysis of alloy steel and Cr(III) bearing ores and minerals in presence of Al(III),

Si(IV), Cr(III), U(VI), Ph(II), Pd(II), Co(II) and Th(IV) and many other ions. In ternary extraction at 0.16 M HCl, tolerance limits of the ions are increased to 50-fold amount in presence of fluoride ion. All other ions have shown almost no interference in all the three systems. Tolerance limits with 4 ppm vanadium(V) for binary and ternary complexes have been determined at pH 3.2, 1.8 M HCl and 0.16 M HCl; the absorbances were measured at 470 nm, 595 nm and 630 nm for the respective complexes (Table 1).

Composition, extraction and stability constants : The vanadium(V) : N-AHA ratio in the binary and ternary complexes was first determined by continuous variation and mole-ratio methods in absence or presence of excess thiocyanate using equimolar solutions (1.96×10^{-3} M) of metal and reagent, and 0.26 M solution of thiocyanate. The composition was always found to be 1 : 2 [V(V) : N-AHA] at 470, 535 and 630 nm. The metal : SCN composition was determined to be 1 : 1 by absorptiometric method at 630 nm using 0.26 M thiocyanate solution. A new absorptiometric method based on Beer's law was employed for the evaluation of extraction constants, K_{ex} , of the binary vanadium(V) chelates involved in binary and ternary complexes as well as extraction

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS [V(V)=0.1 mg, N-AHA=0.1 to 1% IN mibk, 2% NH₄SCN Solution]

Ions	Tolerance limits, ppm		
	pH 3.2 470 nm	1.8 M HCl 595 nm	pH 0.95 630 nm
Acetate	800	900	10,000
Fluoride	400	450	5,000
Tartrate	2,000	5,000	3,000
Oxalate	120	250	500
Citrate	2,000	5,000	3,000
EDTA	50	50	400
Thiourea	1,000	1,000	1,800
Phosphate	750	750	1,000
Fe(III)	Int.	Int.	Int.
Ti(IV)	Int.	Int.	Int. (200, F ⁻)
Mo(VI)	Int.	100	Int. (100, F ⁻)
W(VI)	Int.	100	Int. (100, F ⁻)
Zr(IV)	Int.	50	Int. (200, F ⁻)
Hf(IV)	Int.	Int.	—
Th(IV)	400	500	1,000
Nb(V)	Int.	Int.	Int. (50, F ⁻)
Ta(V)	Int.	Int.	Int. (125, F ⁻)
UO ₂ (II)	1,500	1,500	500
Co(II)	1,000	1,000	1,000
Ni(II)	500	500	1,000
Cu(II)	300	300	500
Mn(II)	180	125	200
Al(III)	750	1,500	1,000
Cr(III)	250	500	500
Bi(III)	100	100	200
In(III)	250	250	400
Zn(II)	1,500	750	1,500
Gd(II)	250	250	500
Hg(II)	200	200	250
Pb(II)	3,500	3,500	1,500
Pd(II)	100	225	450

* Masked with fluoride.

constant, K_{anion} for thiocyanate ligand anion. The extraction or stability constant of the ternary chelate

TABLE 2—STABILITY AND EXTRACTION CONSTANTS OF VANADIUM(V) CHELATES WITH N-AHA AND THIOCYANATE BY PHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Methods/Composition	1 : 2 [V(V) : N-AHA] at pH 3.2			1 : 2 [V(V) : N-AHA] at 1.8 M HCl			1 : 2 : 1 [V(V) : N-AHA : SCN] at pH 0.95		
	log k_1	log k_2	log K	log k_1	log k_2	log K	log k_{ex}	log k_{anton}	log k_{ex} K_{anton} or log K_{mixed}
Leden's method	2.91	3.91	6.85	2.43	4.40	6.88	—	—	—
Yatsimirskii's method	3.39	3.48	6.87	3.40	3.65	7.05	—	—	—
Absorptiometric method	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.80	3.25	9.05
Harvey-Manning's method	A_m	A_s	C	α	log K	log K_{ex}	$K = \frac{1-\alpha}{4\alpha^2 C^2}$		
	0.886	0.535	$7.852 \times 10^{-5} M$	0.3962	7.40	5.71	$\alpha = \frac{A_m - A_s}{A_m}$		
	0.525	0.135	$7.852 \times 10^{-5} M$	0.7429	6.80	6.60			

was directly evaluated also by the same absorptiometric method. The stepwise stability constants of the 1 : 2 vanadium complexes were obtained by photometric methods developed earlier. The results are summarized in Table 2 and shown in Figs. 3-4.

Determination of vanadium in steel (BAS 64b), rock (Ilmenite mineral), ore (bauxite) : The extractive photometric methods were found excellent for analyses with high selectivity. The methods have been found to be rapid, simple and accurate and excess of Fe(III), Ti(IV) in mixture are masked with fluoride ion. Moreover, the ternary extraction gives high selectivity and the procedures are found useful for the analyses of high-speed steel, ilmenite mineral and bauxite ore. The ilmenite mineral samples were collected from T.N. and Putkapahar, M.P. and bauxite from Indian Oxygen Limited, and

Fig 3. Absorptiometric plots. I : K_{ex} for V(V) N-AHA (pH 3.2), II : K_{ex} for V(V) N-AHA (1.8 M HCl), III : K_{ex} for V(V) N-AHA (pH 0.95), IV : K_{ex} for V(V) SCN (pH 0.95).

Fig. 4. Absorptiometric plots.
I : K_{ex} for V(V) N-AHA (pH 3.2)
II : K_{ex} for V(V) N-AHA (1.8 M HCl)

finely powdered (200 mesh) samples obtained directly after magnetic separation were analysed by spectrophotometric methods. The samples were previously standardized. The results on the analyses by the procedures are found to agree well with each other. From the analyses report it has been found

that the amounts of vanadium present in the samples are as follows :

	BAS steel 64b certified, 1.99% V	Rock (Ilmenite mineral) certified, 0.1% and 0.15% V	Ore (Bauxite) certified, 0.28%
Procedure A	1.96	0.08 0.188	0.26
Procedure B	1.97	0.09 0.138	0.26
Procedure C	1.97	0.09 0.140	0.26

Average of several determinations are given with ± 0.02 as error.

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